

Development Of Basic Science Concept Books Through Problem Based Learning (PBL) Models Based On C-Ple Improving Students' Creative Thinking

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Abstract

One of the problems faced in learning the basic concepts of science in universities, especially the Elementary School Teacher Education study program where the study program produces prospective elementary school teachers who will educate and provide the best and professional education for elementary school level students in the future. In addition, learning the basic concepts of science has not increased students' creative thinking in its implementation. This development research considers the consequences of the influence of basic science concept books taught through the C-PLE-based PBL model to improve students' creative thinking. C-PLE (Class Personal Learning Environment) is an application that is programmed to provide convenience for users, the other side of C-PLE is to contribute to the online learning system during the Pandemic in Indonesia. The development research methodology used is (R&D) Research and Development). Basic Science Concepts through the C-PLE-based PBL model can improve students' creative thinking. Based on data analysis, the book development of basic science concepts through the PBL model was developed based on syntax, social systems, user system processing, and support. The development of the basic science concept book through the PBL model obtained content valid results with a value of 4.5% with a feasible category. The content feasibility aspect is 3.9% with the category quite feasible and can be implemented. The user's normality test can be seen from the pretest and posttest values of the application of the product showing a positive effect with a value of <0.05 for the student's creative thinking test. C-PLE is an online learning application that is programmed for lecturers and students in managing the online learning environment. The development of this research can be used as a recommendation for other researchers to apply the basic concepts of science through a competent and internationally competitive learning model with global aspects of science and technology.

Introduction

The ability of people to learn is an important characteristic that distinguishes its kind from other types of creatures, the power of people to change themselves is to learn how to change themselves so that they give an impression of themselves., Thorndike, (1931:30). Why do learning require teaching media, learning models and practical learning, this question is answered through the theory of B.F. Skinner that: It is impossible for teachers to teach without learning tools to change behavior based on their experiences, Skinner, (1968) on(V and A 2016).

The negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is changes in all fields, especially in the field of education and other aspects of life. This learning takes into account the unique way of learning of each student and provides autonomy for each student to plan their learning process, to determine learning activities, to monitor and evaluate their learning outcomes independently in the current era of rapid technological development. ICT-based e-learning supports in improving student pedagogy and cognitive based on the feasibility assessment of the teaching materials used, (S. Sriadhi 2019).

Based on the results of previous research, it was explained that the results of observations in two lectures using textbooks on basic science concepts at a university with the aim of improving science process skills resulted in 60.3% of the scores from the first meeting and 66.9% at the second meeting., (Hayati 2017). The value obtained has not reached maximum completeness for students, with this value still categorized as low. The results of the research that developed the CLIS (Children Learning In Science) model that with this model can improve students' science process skills, the results of the study stated that by calculating the effect size, the value was 3.35, the average student score was 81.17, the N-Gain value was 0, 6 with a medium success rate category. It was explained that the CLIS model is a learning model that seeks to develop ideas and ideas based

on experimental results, so the lecturer gets the value of student learning mastery to improve their science process skills from observation through ideas and ideas formed from the CLIS model, (Rachman 2018).

One of the subjects in the PGSD study program is Elementary Science Basic Concepts which learns about science learning concepts in elementary school. This course has 16 meetings in the third semester and has ten sub-materials which are summarized in a learning book that is systematically arranged based on the existing modules. Studying natural science is not just a mastery of knowledge in the form of facts, principles, or concepts, even a process of discovery, (*Inquiry*), (Pratiwi et al. 2019). Science education is studied to be a vehicle for students to learn more about nature and apply it to everyday life. (Suyanti, 2019). Efforts to improve the quality of education and the quantity of teaching and learning processes as well as the ability of lecturers/teachers in developing scientific literacy and digital technology, namely getting used to living independently with technology, (Xu et al., 2020).

Technology makes lecturers and students able to think critically, (Liliasari 2012), creative thinking, (Retno, 2016), logical thinking, (Hofer and Swan 2014) and have digital literacy skills, (Luthans 2012). Students are able to solve problems in learning, (Surya, et al. 2018), be reflective, (Yus 2017), and resilient in responding to problems and issues in society caused by the impact of technological developments on science, (Carin, A.A. & Sund, 2016; Siswono, 2017; Rahayu, 2017). Based on the results of initial observations of the Semester Final Examination (UAS) for third semester students in the Elementary Science Basic Concepts course in April 2019 before the COVID-19 pandemic, namely class A 87.5%, class B 87%, and class C 86.9%. The results of the initial analysis at the University of Bina Bangsa Getsempena Banda Aceh stated that the use of online facilities and textbooks on Basic Science Concepts at PGSD had not contributed to students effectively, efficiently and practically in implementing the learning models used by lecturers.

Basic Science Concepts are subjects taught to PGSD students to be applied at the elementary school level. PGSD (Elementary School Teacher Education) is a study program that produces prospective teachers to teach at the elementary level and teach several fields of study that are taught in Elementary Schools (SD). Learning Science Basic Concepts includes several materials: 1) the characteristics and diversity of living things, 2) living things and their environment, 3) human organs, 4) the development of living things, 5) the structure of the human body, 6) food, health, disease and prevention, 7) waves and sound, 8) optics, 9) electricity and magnetism, 10) Earth and Space. Learning to solve problems is basically learning by using scientific methods and thinking systematically, logically, practically, and thoroughly, (Surya and Syahputra 2017). The purpose of learning in solving problems is to acquire students' cognitive abilities and skills in a rational, straightforward, and thorough manner. (Padmowihardjo, 2014; Amalia et al., 2017). Each learning behavior is characterized by specific characteristics of change, behavior, stimulus, and response to the influence of the learning environment. (Tohirin, 2001; Miguel et al., 1992). Changes that occur in the learning environment are related to experiences and practices that are carried out intentionally and consciously, (Aprikustianita, 2018).

Technological progress is a process of interaction, (Krahenbuhl 2019) and the reach of human thought is able to reach all levels of society in any part of the world and become increasingly open, (Daryanto Setiawan, 2017; Pangondian R. A. et al., 2019). The ability to think creatively in technology means being able to construct how to think long term, (Bruce, Weil, and Calhoun 2015), have the ability of science process skills both students and lecturers, (Tantu and Christi 2020).

In order for this research to focus on the problem in question, the following research questions were used:

1. How the validity of the Development of the Basic Science Concept Book through the C-PLE-based PBL model improves students' creative thinking.
2. How is the practicality of developing the Basic Science Concept Book through the C-PLE-based PBL model to improve students' creative thinking.
3. How is the effectiveness of the Development of Basic Science Concept Books through the C-PLE-based PBL model in increasing students' creative thinking.

This development research aims to develop the ability of lecturers in technology class management, providing support in the teaching and learning process with learning tools, developing textbooks to increase student creativity through C-PLE as an attraction in online-based learning, and testing students' soft skills in solving various problems in learning.

Theoretical Review

The Basic Science Concept course discusses the science material taught in elementary schools (SD). Natural Sciences is also called the word "Science" (science) taken from the Latin word *scientia* which literally means "knowledge". Science as a process of knowledge and is the steps taken by scientists to conduct investigations and research in search of explanations of natural phenomena. These steps are: formulating problems, formulating hypotheses, designing experiments, collecting data, analyzing and finally concluding. Science education has experienced a shift that places more emphasis on the teaching and learning process, (Tawil. and Liliasari 2013). Bruner (on Sagala, 2006; on Tawil: 4: 2014) the learning process can be

distinguished in three phases, namely: 1) Information, each lesson gets and seeks information is increasing knowledge and everyone can expand and deepen knowledge through the information, 2) Transformation, the information held is transformed into a contextual abstract form of transformation to be used in broader matters, 3) Evaluation, to understand the knowledge gained and the transformation that can be used in understanding other phenomena. (Sudjana, 1991 on Sudatha, 2020). The nature of science is the foundation on which to learn science. There are many ways that can be done to achieve the aspects contained in science, namely using the concept of constructivism-based learning, (Sumarauw, Ibrahim, and Prastowo 2017).

Problem Based Learning (PBL) model is a learning model centered on a problem but still has a specific goal of solving problems in order to achieve learning objectives, (Harris 2019). according to Trianto (2015:51), The learning model is a pattern and plan that is used as a guide for carrying out classroom learning or learning in tutorials. John Dewey's view, that changing student knowledge is an act of cognitive, personal, social, cultural change centered on the experience of students, (Thayer, 1985; Sikandar, 2016). ***Problem Based Learning (PBL), where the teacher acts as a guide on the side rather than sage on the stage. This emphasizes the importance of learning aids in the early stages of learning. This view connects various teaching models called the constructivist perspective (constructivist perspective) which demands a change in learning behavior from teachers to students,*** (Arends 2012). The essence of Problem Based Learning (PBL) in the form of presenting various authentic and meaningful problematic situations to students which can serve as a springboard for investigations and investigations. Scientists who developed Problem Based Learning (PBL), is: (Cognition & Technology Group at Vanderbilt. 1990, 1996a, 1996b; Gordon et al, 2001; Krajcik et al, 2003' Slavin, Madden, Dolan, & Wasik, 1994: Torp & Sage, 1998) dalam (Arends, 2012: 42:43) describes that this Instructional model has the following features:

Problem Based Learning Features

No	Feature	Statement
1	Stimulation	The stimulus statement that PBL organize teaching around problems that are socially and personally meaningful to students. They face various life situations and competing solutions to solve them.
2	Interdisciplinary focus	PBL focuses on a specific subject (science, mathematics, history), problems are investigated to explore many subjects.
3	Authentic investigation	Problem Based Learning (PBL) requires students to conduct authentic investigations that seek to find real solutions to real problems.
4	Artifact production and exhibit	Problem Based Learning (PBL) requires students to construct products in the form of artifacts and exhibits.
5	Collaboration	Problem Based Learning (PBL) provides opportunities for students to collaborate.

Personal Learning Environment (PLE) is not a new concept, but with technological developments such as blogs, (Glaserfeld, 1995; Attwell, 2007), social bookmarking, wikis, podcasts, social software (internet networks), (Egan et al. 2015), web application programming interface, (Sriadhi 2016). The most interesting thing about the Personal Learning Environment (PLE) is developing educational technology that can respond to the way people use technology to learn and that allows them to shape their own learning space, (ROACH 2010); and form and join peer or peer communities and make work more flexible, (Nesbit, Li, and Leacock 2005); consuming, mixing, from sharing material, (Kuntarto, 2017; Purnomo et al., 2016).

Thinking is an active and coordinated processing ability. Thinking is a process of thinking ability that runs continuously including the interaction of a series of thoughts and perceptions. Thinking skills should be

developed from an early age through learning because to instill character in students from an early age is the teacher's obligation so that students are able to think creatively and critically, analytically, and provide conclusions or solve problems in everyday life. (Angraini and Sani 2015). The three key components assessed in creativity using the TTCT are fluency, flexibility and novelty. Fluency refers to the number of ideas that are generated in response to a command. The ability to think creatively is a creative and analytical design process that provides opportunities to create a prototype model, experiment with prototype models, and redesign after receiving feedback. (Sinaga, 2020).

The role of the problem in (PBL) is in the form of assignments from basic science concept material which will be poured into a practicum, so that it will activate lecturers and PBL model books as a complement to science learning facilities. Students are expected to gain knowledge through collaboration, namely by discussing among themselves and playing an important role in group assignments. Learning will take place conducive and produce the desired learning achievement in accordance with the curriculum. Class Personal Learning Environment (C-PLE) as a web-based learning tool acts as an online learning tool capable of providing higher (pedagogic) knowledge in providing and attracting learning content. Students gain knowledge through content and new things through the device as an online medium that is structured like a private room. Students are able to operate the device as well as possible taking and receiving links or content that has been sent. The implementation of the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model on the PLE web provides a new atmosphere for learning styles in the personal environment of students who now prioritize online/online learning. By building broad and flexible knowledge, developing skills in solving problems effectively, and developing independent learning skills.

Research methods

This research method is Research and Development R&D. In the research development model, Ploom, (1997) on (Sinaga et al., 2019), is: contains a systematic guide to the steps taken by researchers so that the product designed has a feasibility standard, (Sugiyono 2018). The results of development research are not only to develop an existing product but also to find knowledge or answers to practical problems. Research and development methods are also defined as a research method used to produce certain products, and test the effectiveness of these products, (Sugiyono 2017). The assessment data on the analysis of the Basic Science Concepts material was analyzed descriptively quantitatively. The formula used is as follows:

$$P = \frac{\Sigma q}{\Sigma r}$$

Description:

P = The score obtained from the standard assessment component of the contents of the basic science concept textbooks.

Σq = The number of concepts marked with (√) in the Basic Science Concepts textbook.

Σr = The number of indicators in the Basic Science Concepts textbook.

In this study, the rating scale used is 1 to 5, where the lowest score is 1 and the highest score is 5. The determination of the range can be determined through the range of the highest score minus the range of the lowest score divided by the highest score.

Results and Discussion

The results of this study resulted in the development of a textbook on Basic Science Concepts through the C-PLE-based PBL model to improve valid, practical and effective creative thinking skills. The stages carried out in the research development process are the preparation of university standard learning tools, namely (RPS) based on the material for the Basic Concepts of Science for one semester.

Results of the Investigation Stage of the Basic Science Concept Book

1. Quality and material input
2. Language Quality.
3. Quality of material out put.
4. Clarity of content and purpose.
5. Conformity of the number of outputs with the indicators of science material.

Science Material Book Validation Value

No	Assessment Aspect	Average Aspect Value Indicator or						Total Average Score
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	
1	Material quality and input	4,5	4,4	4,5	4,6	4,5	4,4	4,3

2	Quality Language	4, 3	4, 2	4, 3	4, 1	4, 1	4, 2	4,2
3	Output/reporting quality	4, 2	4	4, 3	4, 3	4, 0	4, 1	4,3
4	clarity of content and purpose	4, 3	4, 2	4, 3	4, 3	4, 4	4, 4	4,3
5	Conformity of the number of outputs with the indicators of science material	4, 2	4	4, 3	4, 0	4, 3	4, 4	4,3
Average Value Aspect Validation								4,3

Average indicators in the table. 4.3 is obtained from the results of the assessment scores of each aspect that is assessed with the assessment criteria on the validation instrument. The results of the number and distribution of results for each indicator are provided by experts and practitioners. Furthermore, the P1 value as the average value is 4.3 which is declared valid for the assessment of the Basic Science Concept Materials book as a lecturer handbook that is suitable for use. The percentage of assessments from the aspect of science material indicators can be illustrated through the diagram below:

PLE class is a facility provided by lecturers in facilitating and providing flexibility for student learning in a transparent manner both in terms of material, student process skills and the evaluation stage given by lecturers to students. (Attwell 2007; Bidarra and Sousa 2020; Hicks and Sinkinson 2015; Korhonen, Ruhalahti, and Veermans 2019). Students are facilitated by the PLE class with the aim of introducing new devices, especially in one Constitutional Court which is managed by the supporting lecturer, so that there is a collaboration between lecturers and students. Transparency of grades and assignment reports given by lecturers will give students cognitive flexibility so that there will be an increase in student creativity in managing their personal learning. (Jati Laksono, Ashadi, and Saputro 2016; Muasaroh 2016). All reports and study assignments for one semester are neatly organized and can make daily and monthly study reports for one semester. This is done as a basic effort to increase the success of implementing C-PLE in a process and gradual manner which is the key to successful use in learning (Mudjia Rahardjo 2018; Nurrita 2018; Sutarto 2017). The test results can be seen in the table in the form of descriptive data from the PLE Class test results on student creativity based on science process skills through evaluations carried out in two classes, namely the experimental class and the control class. The experimental class is treated using the PLE class and the control class using academic facilities such as the portal: opensimka.com. C-PLE test results with SPSS test.

C-PLE Based Student Creativity Test Results

Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Creative Thinking Experiment Class	40.067	45	2.8556	.4257
	Creative Thinking Control Class	39.333	45	2.6371	.3931

The data above shows that descriptively the information obtained through creativity testing can be seen for the two classes that there is no significant difference. This shows almost similar conditions for the two classes. This descriptive description becomes the initial basis for thinking to be able to increase creativity from the use of the C-PLE-based science basic concept book product. From the standard deviation, it can be seen that the value of the distribution of data on each variable. Std Deviation is used to measure the high level of creative thinking of students, the greater the value, the higher the level of creative thinking of students for each material in the Basic Science Concepts book.

Conclusion

Internalization of learning activities Basic Science Concepts. In the subject of Basic Science Concepts, students are also taught through various phenomena. The stages of learning Basic Science Concepts are also a key to the success of using PLE Class in learning so that students are able to obtain better learning outcomes. The use of the PLE Class-based PBL model in learning can be said to be practical and effective. The effectiveness of the PBL model used in learning Basic Science Concepts is based on the application of learning carried out during learning, is:

1. The ability of lecturers to manage the class technologically.
2. Learning tools that support the teaching and learning process.
3. Development of textbooks that increase student creativity.
4. The introduction of the C-PLE application has a superior learning appeal.
5. The ability of academic soft skills in solving problems.

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